

CURRENT ISSUES OF TRAINING ON THE "CITIZEN INTERACTION MODULE" IN PERSONNEL PREPARATION FOR INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES

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Abstract: The author has studied scholars' opinions on organizing training based on the "Citizen Interaction Module" for professional personnel in internal affairs bodies and has developed proposals and recommendations.

Keywords: Internal affairs bodies, professional personnel, citizen interaction module, professional structure.

In order to organize training based on the "Citizen Interaction Module" for professional personnel in internal affairs bodies, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 20, 2023, No. PQ-10 "On additional measures to transform internal affairs bodies into a people-oriented professional structure and direct them to work in closer cooperation with the population," as well as the Order of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 28, 2023, No. 98 "On organizing a system of continuous training for employees of crime prevention, traffic patrol, and patrol-post service units of internal affairs bodies on the 'Citizen Interaction Module'" have established the continuous training process for employees of the aforementioned services who directly interact with citizens at the Institute of Advanced Training of the Ministry of Internal Affairs.

The tasks of the Ministry of Internal Affairs and its departments for effectively organizing the continuous training process on the "Citizen Interaction Module" have been defined. Specifically, to assess employees' competency for field service, continuous training in traditional format will be organized at the Institute of Advanced Training of the Ministry of Internal Affairs on general and special modules once every three years, separating employees from service. This training aims to develop necessary practical skills in communication psychology, culture of behavior, and maintaining mental stability in non-standard situations, as well as to strengthen employees' intellectual and professional competence in making prompt and fair decisions in potential non-standard situations with citizens. Employees who successfully pass the final tests of the training course will receive certificates granting them the right to serve in this field in the future, thereby increasing their personal responsibility for effective service within the system.

Based on the set goals and objectives, professors and teachers of the Institute for Advanced Training of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan prepared "Special training programs for improving the qualifications of employees of the Law Enforcement Prevention Service and the Road Patrol Service and the Patrol Post Service of the Ministry of Internal Affairs in the "Civil Work Module" and approved it in accordance with the established procedure.

To ensure the implementation of these programs, the teaching staff of the institute developed themes, prepared and implemented in the educational process teaching and

methodological complexes (based on case studies, brainstorming, simulation (imitation) interactive methods) with QR code for problem situations on each topic.

Also, methodological rooms (methodical cabinet) were created for these areas of service, and special tutors were trained from among professors and teachers with many years of practical experience in the specified areas of service.

When organizing training in the "Citizenship Module," the educational process is organized in the form of interactive and non-traditional simulation classes based on advanced pedagogical, information and communication, and innovative pedagogical technologies, based on modern teaching methods, taking into account the specifics of sectoral services, qualified professors and teachers of leading higher educational institutions of the republic, psychologists, and specialists of relevant sectoral services of the Ministry of Internal Affairs are involved in the training in the prescribed manner.

The following newly appointed specialists to the field services are attracted to the training courses according to the Module, as a rule, after three years: graduates of the undergraduate level of full-time and correspondence education of the Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, graduates of the Faculty of Professional Training of the Institute for Advanced Training, graduates of the University of Public Safety of the Republic of Uzbekistan, who have completed the specialty of command and tactical activities of the road patrol and patrol-post services.

Students involved in the training courses have the right to acquire the knowledge provided for in the training program, make proposals to the management and faculty on further improving the educational process, improving the system of professional development, participate in spiritual, educational and cultural events, receive additional information and consultations related to professional development, use the information resource center, classrooms and computer equipment of the educational institution, appeal to the supervisor on the results of the final test (examination).

In the system of continuous professional development in the "Citizenship Module," the educational process is carried out in accordance with the requirements of state educational requirements, curricula and programs, as well as other legislative acts, as well as the Charter of the educational institution. The educational process is organized by dividing the trainees involved in the training courses into separate subgroups by sectoral services.

Training sessions will be held in the traditional form, in general and special blocks in the areas of crime prevention, road patrol and patrol service, based on the curriculum and program designed for 144 hours.

The general block of training sessions is organized in accordance with the "Code of Professional Culture and Service Discipline of Internal Affairs Officers" and physical and combat, communication culture, psychological and legal training for all areas of activity according to the module, designed for 36 hours.

The special block is designed for 104 hours and is organized in the form of individual situational training sessions for each area of activity in modules related to the process of communication between employees and citizens in non-standard and complex problem situations.

During training sessions, students' knowledge is assessed through intermediate and final assessments. The intermediate test is taken at the end of each module, and regardless of

the type of module, students who have not received a positive grade on two or more modules are not allowed to take the final exam at the end of the block.

The training sessions are organized in the form of seminars, independent learning, and practical classes, taking into account the specifics of each module.

Based on the specifics of industry services, training sessions are organized in the form of interactive and non-traditional simulation classes based on advanced pedagogy, information and communication technologies, and innovative pedagogical technologies based on modern teaching methods.

In particular: for combat and physical training - departments for coordination of special exercises and physical and combat training, for legal training - the Academy of the Ministry, for information technology - the Center for Cybersecurity, for information technology, communication and information protection, as well as for communications with the public and mass media, psychologists of the psychological support department.

Also, for the activities of crime prevention - the Crime Prevention Service and the Center for Scientific and Practical Research on Public Safety, for the activities of the road patrol service - the Road Traffic Safety Service, for the activities of the patrol and post service - the Public Order Protection Service.

In addition, as a result of such cooperation, qualified professors-teachers and psychologists from other leading higher educational institutions of the republic are also involved in training, which serves to increase the level of professional training of employees.

The curricula reflect teaching methods and innovative pedagogical technologies that provide for the formation of professional competence necessary for students through situational practical exercises, rapid decision-making in non-standard conditions, correct assessment of the situation, communication psychology, as well as in the process of using physical force, special means and firearms.

The quality of the educational process and the content of education are studied by the management of the Institute and employees of the Department of Organization of the Educational Process of the Department of Spiritual and Educational Work and Human Resources in accordance with the current regulatory legal acts through planned and extra-curricular pedagogical controls.

It is established that materials and statistical data on problematic situations arising in the process of working with citizens in sectoral services, cases discussed on social networks, are provided to the Institute quarterly by the Department of Public Security of the Ministry and the Service for Spiritual and Educational Work of the Department of Spiritual and Educational Work and Human Resources.

Every six months, the institute develops a plan for conducting situational training sessions on problematic situations related to the activities of industry services, a scenario, a set of cases, and methods that include a unified solution.

Situational training sessions conducted for each module have been recorded, video clips have been developed, and are being used during training sessions.

At the end of the training, final exams will be accepted for each branch of service.

During the module, final tests will be taken to determine whether students have mastered the modules and topics provided for in the curriculum and curricula, as well as their ability to work in this industry in the future. According to the schedule approved by the head of the Institute, the final tests will be held in special classrooms equipped with special

technical means for each branch of service or in open spaces where certain situations and situations are modulated. The final tests are scheduled to be filmed on video. Final examinations are accepted by commissions consisting of responsible heads of sectoral services, experienced managers and professors-teachers of educational institutions of the Ministry, other higher educational institutions in the field of teaching and methodological work.

The order of approval of the head of the Department of Spiritual and Educational Affairs and Human Resources for accepting the final tests has been established.

On the first day of students' involvement in the training courses, the secretary of the commission conducts consultations on the conditions of the final examination, evaluation criteria and the procedure for the examination before the start of the examination.

If listeners cannot participate in the final tests for valid reasons, they are obliged to notify the secretary of the commission immediately. Students who did not take the test for valid reasons may participate in the tests taken from another study group or in the test taken at the end of the next academic year.

Before the start of each training course for the final exams of the module, the Institute developed a set of practical and theoretical questions and assignments for the test exam.

The final test questions and assignments used at the end of the current training courses will be updated by at least 30 percent for the next training courses, based on the problematic situations in practice.

Students who successfully complete the final exams for the module will be issued a certificate of the specified sample. Employees who have received a certificate will have the right to work in the sectoral services in which they previously worked for the next three years.

Listeners who have not been certified due to a negative score on the final exam will be allowed once to repass the final exams if they have passed the intermediate exams to good and excellent grades.

The results of the final interview are drawn up in the form of a statement signed by the secretary and members of the commission and approved by the chairman of the commission.

Employees who have not received a certificate due to a negative assessment from the final tests will be recognized as not having mastered the curricula for the training module, and within three working days, a notification will be sent on behalf of the head of the Institute to the Department of Spiritual and Educational Work and Human Resources and territorial divisions.

In accordance with the requirements of the "Regulations on the procedure for serving in internal affairs bodies," approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 29, 2017 No. PP-3413, the issue of staying or not staying in the service in the internal affairs bodies is considered by the extraordinary attestation commissions in the structural divisions and territorial divisions of the Ministry.

At the end of the module, employees who have advanced their qualifications, regardless of whether they have received a certificate or not, are entered into the electronic information platform "E-educational module" by the secretaries of the commission.

At this point, it should be noted that the documents collected for each advanced training course organized according to the module are stored in the file in the prescribed

manner for a period of three years. The certificate is attached to the employee's personal file and serves as the basis for working in this industry for the next three years.

Employees who are dissatisfied with the results of the final test can appeal to the appellate commission within one day after the announcement of the test results. Complaints submitted to the Appeals Commission shall be considered from the date of their receipt in the presence of the candidate who appealed within the period established by legislation. If the complaint is recognized as valid, the record signed by the commission shall be amended accordingly and a certificate shall be issued to the employee. During the consideration of the complaint, the significance of the final test score given to the employee in the record is preserved. The conclusion adopted as a result of the complaint review is considered the final decision.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the staff of the Institute of Advanced Training of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, in cooperation with the relevant sectoral services of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, using the available opportunities, are mobilizing all their strength, energy, and expertise to increase the effectiveness and impact of service activities. They aim to achieve genuine satisfaction of the population by educating employees of the internal affairs bodies based on the principle of "For Human Dignity" as representatives of the state with high spiritual and moral qualities, loyal to their duty, patriotic and people-oriented. This is achieved through the systematic and continuous organization of spiritual and educational work based on the principle "from educational institution to the end of service."

References:

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